

The quality of service assessment of eMBB and mMTC traffic in a clustered 5G ecosystem of a smart factory

Viacheslav Kovtun^{1,*}, Oksana Kovtun², Krzysztof Grochla¹, Oleh Yasniy³

¹ Internet of Things Group, Institute of Theoretical and Applied Informatics Polish Academy of Sciences, Gliwice, Poland

² Department of the Theory and Practice of Translation, Faculty of Foreign Languages, Vasyl' Stus Donetsk National University, Vinnytsia, Ukraine

³ Department of Mathematical Methods in Engineering, Ternopil Ivan Puluj National Technical University, Ternopil, Ukraine

* Corresponding author: kovtun_v_v@vntu.edu.ua (V.K.)

Abstract: Industry 4.0 demands seamless integration of smart factories with the Industrial Internet of Things (IIoT), reliant on robust communication infrastructure. Leveraging 5G's support for enhanced Mobile Broadband (eMBB), massive Machine Type Communication (mMTC), and Network Slicing (NS), this study explores quality of service assurance within a clustered 5G ecosystem of a smart factory. The article proposes two new multi-parameter scenarios for allocating the entire channel pool between different types of requests (mMTC, eMBB) for the model of an integrated open 5G cluster. The scenario with isolation does not allow channel reassignment between requests of different types or originating zones (handover or from the coverage area of the target 5G cluster), while the virtual scenario allows such reassignment. It is shown that using these scenarios, the stationary distribution of probabilities of states of the corresponding two-dimensional Markov chains has a multiplicative form. An information technology has been developed to calculate QoS indicators for different types of requests using these channel allocation scenarios. Studies have been conducted on the effectiveness of using one or another access strategy depending on the loads on the 5G cluster. Based on the proposed mathematical apparatus, the information technology enables finding the optimal scenario for channel allocation, as well as calculating the parameters' values for such a scenario.

Keywords: Industrial Internet of Things; smart factory; clustered 5G ecosystem; eMBB technology; mMTC technology; Network Slicing; quality of service; Markov chain.

1 Introduction and State-of-the-Art

1.1. Relevance of the Research

According to statistics from Strategy Analytics, Inc., in 2021, the global IIoT market exceeded \$263 billion and is projected to reach \$1.11 trillion by 2028 [1]. In a broad sense, IIoT [2-6] constitutes a system that integrates smart equipment, employees, and cloud data. Through thousands of sensors installed in the industry and corresponding software, production can be automated, and its processes can be managed. Specifically, it enables quality control in production by selecting optimal operation modes for manufacturing chains. It also allows monitoring the condition of equipment to predict wear and potential breakdowns, enabling timely replacement of parts, extending equipment lifespan, and preventing downtime due to failures. Based on data analysis, targeted increases in workload can be implemented, thereby enhancing productivity. Some IIoT technologies enable the modelling of reality and testing various scenarios first in a virtual environment.

Let's explore how mobile technologies contribute to the integration of smart manufacturing with the Industrial Internet of Things (IIoT). For the everyday consumer, the adoption of the 5G platform [7-11] primarily translates into a significant boost in connectivity speed. This increase in internet browsing speed, powered by the inherent high bandwidth of 5G, is readily apparent. Moreover, the ability of 5G to facilitate real-time streaming of high-definition videos on mobile devices is widely recognized. However, the implications of reduced latency and enhanced connection reliability are often met with a more subdued response from regular users: a decrease in the delay when loading a webpage from 50 ms to 10 ms may go unnoticed by the average consumer.

In the realm of integrating mobile communication technologies into manufacturing, the landscape is notably intricate. Historically, mobile communication systems haven't been extensively integrated into scenarios involving the Industrial Internet of Things (IIoT). While the network speed of 4G [7-9] adequately caters to users' demands for on-the-go video streaming, its capabilities in ensuring network reliability and latency still fall short of meeting the requirements of the majority of industrial settings. In industrial contexts, 4G is often employed for transmitting production process data to the cloud, albeit not in real-time. For instance, machines and equipment within a factory typically transmit sensor data to a central terminal every 10-20 seconds, which then periodically forwards data summaries to the cloud platform using 4G. To maintain the stability of this data transmission process, many factories continue to rely on cable connections. While this approach is reliable, it entails significant costs and contributes to a complex, static infrastructure that resists modernization without substantial investments. However, as mobile communication systems enhance their performance to the point where they can replace cable connections based on a combination of quality parameters, the internal structure complexity of enterprises

will diminish. Consequently, this will bolster management efficiency, elevate productivity, and curtail operational and production modernization expenses.

Currently, the technical standards of 5G emerge as the most suitable for meeting the communication channel requirements in industrial systems [12-14]. The inherently low latency of 5G ensures real-time monitoring and control needs in the industrial sector are met. Its high-reliability network quality guarantees stability, while its ample bandwidth enables real-time transmission of high-definition 2D video and augmented reality space visualization, significantly enhancing the precision of remote control operations. With substantial investments in Industry 4.0 implementation globally [15-17], the synergy between 5G and the Industrial Internet of Things (IIoT) emerges as a highly promising avenue for scientific exploration. Of particular significance is the evaluation of service quality for both equipment-to-equipment (mMTC like) and operator-to-operator (eMBB like) requests, given the extensive investments in Industry 4.0 worldwide [15-17].

1.2. State-of-the-Art

Numerous research papers have extensively examined the Radio Resource allocation (RRA) and management techniques employed in widely used 5G networks [18-20]. Various research endeavours have explored and assessed the RRA, as well as the quality of service (QoS) provisions specifically designed for 5G networks [21-25]. At the same time, we note the characteristic trend of recent years, which consists in the fact that the communication resources of the investigated 5G networks are represented by sets of segments obtained as a result of the use of Network Slicing (NS) technology.

Recent studies have presented and deliberated upon RRA strategies and challenges associated with NS [18-20]. In [18], a comprehensive survey of principles and a model addressing RRA for NS were explored. Meanwhile, [19] delved into the equitable distribution of 5G resources among various network slices. The investigation in [21] focused on NS within virtualized wireless networks. Additionally, an algorithm for RRA was proposed in the context of orthogonal frequency division multiple access virtual radio access networks. This algorithm aims to enhance the spectral efficiency of enhanced Mobile Broadband (eMBB) and ultra-Reliable Low Latency Communication (uRLLC) slices while simultaneously improving uRLLC reliability.

[26] introduced three scheduling schemes tailored for software-defined NS, aiming to improve the resolution of the joint RRA problem while accommodating diverse QoS requirements. Meanwhile, [20] proposed a packet delay modelling approach in the 5G network to attain resource fairness and high utilization. This modelling focused on the traffic flow through a series of virtual network functions.

Additionally, [27] showcased a 5G NS framework designed to facilitate effective isolation, addressing the simultaneous existence of IoT and eMBB slices.

In [20], the focus is on discussing the RRA method tailored for NS. Specifically, a dynamic model for allocating network resources across diverse 5G slices across various 5G network domains is put forth. Given unique specifications for each 5G slice in Cloud Radio Access Network (CRAN), the proposed RRA methodology strives to enhance satisfaction levels for every traffic slice within CRAN and across every segment within the 5G network.

The authors of [22] establish an innovative slicing architecture for the 5G network with the primary goal of simplifying the comprehension of 5G. Furthermore, they introduce a model designed to manage constraints arising from spectrum sharing among various access networks. This effort contributes to a better understanding of 5G and addresses challenges associated with spectrum sharing in diverse access network environments.

Within [24], a comprehensive examination is undertaken to understand the end-to-end behaviour of slice isolation, with a particular emphasis on the security perspective. The isolations are categorized into distinct types, including traffic, bandwidth, processing, and storage. The paper delves into a discussion of the challenges associated with the current trends in the isolation of 5G slices, highlighting the authors' perspective on isolation as a paramount property within NS.

In their work [19, 25], the authors proposed a versatile model capable of handling diverse data types. Subsequently, addressing different data types necessitates the implementation of a traffic scheduling technique, thereby facilitating the management of QoS in 5G mobile networks. The recommended techniques include first-in-first-out queuing, priority queuing, and weighted fair queuing.

In the context of [24], a queueing model is postulated to interact with two different packet categories: real-time and non-real-time.. Each packet category is designated a specific transmission time, during which a scheduler assigns the packet to a corresponding baseband resource unit. Notably, the queueing model prioritizes real-time packets, and this heightened priority is conveyed to the queueing model via frequency feedback, thereby influencing the packets transmission.

In [23], a novel and secure authentication framework for service-oriented environments. is put forward, designed to efficiently support both NS and fog computing within the context of a 5G-enabled IoT network.

[28] introduces a dynamic NS framework featuring a regional orchestrator responsible for coordinating the distribution of workloads among local fog nodes.

Within this framework, the size of each slice can be dynamically modified based on energy availability and service requests.

[20] presents an innovative NS architecture optimizing the utilization of spectrum resources in both licensed and unlicensed frequency bands.

Meanwhile, [21] proposes a framework for optimization capable of jointly RRA for slices, considering both cloud processing power and network bandwidth at a fine-grained level. This framework aims to optimize resource utilization for enhanced performance.

In [22,23], the utilization of queuing models is employed to conceptualize the RRA challenges arising from the simultaneous existence of various services with varying QoS requirements within 4G or 5G networks.

Specifically focusing on the coexistence of equipment-to-equipment and operator-to-operator communications within 4G networks, [22] utilizes a queuing model to analyze the implications of such types of communication coexistence on a 4G system. Meanwhile, [23] proposes the RRA method for equipment-to-equipment and operator-to-operator traffic, implementing a time-controlled scheduling scheme within 4G networks. This method aims to address the complexities of managing resources for both equipment-to-equipment and operator-to-operator communication under dynamic scheduling conditions.

In [24], an analysis of the RRA problem across the primary domains of 5G networks is conducted using a comprehensive queuing model. The suggested approach comprises three sub-queuing models that correspond to the three main domains of the 5G network: CRAN, edge computing, and cloud data centres. Precisely, the model is crafted to predict the required Quality of QoS for network use cases within each element of the 5G architecture.

Meanwhile, [25] introduces the RRA method for 5G use cases within the 5G CRAN framework, employing polling system methods. The main goal of this strategy is to ensure the necessary delay for each specific 5G slice or use case [26, 27].

The authors of [28] present the RRA method that distributes the implementation cost of the network among deployed 5G NS, effectively reducing core network expenses. However, it is noteworthy that this allocation method does not specifically address the QoS considerations for individual 5G slices.

Referring to [29], a scheduling algorithm based on energy efficiency is introduced for URLLC ϕ_{TB} eMBB. Formulated as a mixed-integer non-linear problem, the algorithm demonstrates superior performance compared to existing classical schemes, as evidenced by numerical results.

In [30], the study investigates the effects of the software-defined networking controller on packet delay, with a specific focus on two services: eMBB and massive Machine Type Communications (mMTC). The analytical model employed

suggests that the proposed approach can be utilized to plan RRA methods in 5G edge clouds, ensuring compliance with QoS requirements across all 5G slices [31-33].

Concluding the review of analogs, we will formulate a current concept for the application of 5G in the field of smart manufacturing. 5G networks play a crucial role in enabling smart manufacturing by connecting machine parks, production machines, and factory sites, thus opening up new possibilities for automation, flexibility, and innovative applications [34]. Smart manufacturing involves using internet-connected machinery to monitor the production process, aiming to automate operations and leverage data analytics to enhance manufacturing performance (aligned with SDG 9 – innovation and infrastructure, and SDG 11 – sustainable cities). This approach is a specific application of the industrial Internet of Things (IIoT).

Implementations include installing sensors in machines to collect performance and operational data. Previously, this data was stored locally on individual devices and used only to diagnose equipment failures after they occurred. Now, engineers can analyze real-time data from an entire factory's machines to detect signs of potential failures in specific parts, allowing for preventive maintenance and reducing unplanned downtime. Additionally, engineers can identify inefficiencies or material usage issues by analyzing trends in the data. Data scientists and engineers can also use this information to run simulations of various operations, identifying the most effective and dynamic methods for improving processes [34-36].

The authors in [37, 38] examined smart manufacturing and the IIoT as key components for achieving cyber-physical manufacturing systems (CPMS) due to the vast amount of data generated during the manufacturing process. To achieve real-time transmission and processing of this massive data (aligned with SDG 9 – innovation and infrastructure), the authors highlighted the communication technology requirements for CPMS: high transmission rate, high reliability, low latency, high security, extensive coverage, and the ability to support a large number of connections. 5G communication systems are uniquely equipped to enable IIoT-based CPMS manufacturing because 3G and 4G technologies fall short of meeting CPMS requirements. Additionally, the authors explored manufacturing scenarios under three key 5G use cases: eMBB, mMTC, and uRLLC.

Let's summarize our fairly detailed review of research focused on evaluating QoS requests in 5G networks, specifically catering to the information service needs of objects that include industrial sensor networks. First and foremost, it's worth noting that the combination of QoS-5G-NS-IoT is directly addressed only in works [30-33]. However, when mentioning 5G technologies such as uRLLC, eMBB,

mMTC, authors prefer to study their impact on QoS separately. In some works, the QoS of joint uRLLC and eMBB traffic is investigated. The typical situation for a smart factory with active IIoT usage, where it is necessary to assess the quality of service of eMBB and mMTC traffic explicitly, is not explicitly considered. In the closest analogue [30], the issue of communication resource allocation in a 5G network with joint eMBB and mMTC traffic is explored, rather than the problem of evaluating the quality of its service. It is important to note separately that in all the aforementioned studies, the 5G network is perceived as a holistic phenomenon. At the same time, the 5G network has a clustered structure, driven by the use of base stations as the physical foundation of the network. Ignoring this fact in the case of modelling the 5G ecosystem of a smart factory with a large number of IIoT subscribers and massive operators' traffic is unacceptable. Thus, the results presented below are relevant and adequate in the context of the formulated research theme.

1.3. Main attributes of the research

The object of the research is the process of evaluating the quality of service for eMBB and mMTC requests within an instance of a clustered 5G ecosystem, taking into account the characteristics of its load.

The subject of the research includes the theory of teletraffic, queuing theory, renewal theory, Markov chain theory, and numerical methods.

The research objective can be formulated as follows: to analytically formalize a metric for evaluating the quality of service for internal and external eMBB and mMTC requests within the target cluster of the 5G ecosystem, taking into account scenarios for processing typed requests, methods of communication resource segmentation, and load parameters.

Let's summarize the content of the section by formulating the main contribution of the research. The study is based on three key technologies of the 5G platform crucial for Industry 4.0: eMBB, mMTC, and NS. NS technology allows the organization of the communication space within the 5G ecosystem's base stations, designed to ensure a defined level of quality of service for informational interaction in the cyberspace of a smart factory. It is considered that, to guarantee the established level of quality of service, the switching resources of the 5G ecosystem can be organized according to two scenarios: a scenario with Isolated Network Segments (INS) and a scenario with Virtual Network Segments (VNS). Considering the clustered structure of the 5G ecosystem in a smart factory, we examine four admissible classes of session setup requests: internal (within the target 5G cluster) and external (redirected to the target 5G cluster) eMBB requests, as well as internal and external mMTC requests. The article presents interpretations of metrics for assessing the quality of service for each of the

identified request types, taking into account which of the two scenarios for processing eMBB and mMTC requests is implemented in the investigated 5G ecosystem. Analytical expressions for calculating quality indicators as part of the metrics are formalized based on the stationary probability distributions of states in corresponding two-dimensional Markov chains.

The article is structured as follows. In Section 2.1, we formalize the parameter space to adequately describe the research object. Following this, in Section 2.2, we formalize the method for calculating a quality of service metric for an instance of a smart factory 5G ecosystem operating within the INS (Isolated Network Segments) scenario. In Section 2.3, we formalize the method for calculating a quality of service metric for an instance of a smart factory 5G ecosystem operating within the VNS (Virtual Network Segments) scenario. It's worth noting that the specifics of these scenarios are defined in Section 2.1. Finally, in Section 3, we implement a numerical experiment to justify the effectiveness of the created mathematical apparatus.

2 Materials and Methods

2.1. Statement of the Research

The Industry 4.0 paradigm defines the future of industrial production in the format of tightly integrating smart factories and IIoT. The informational component of this integration should be based on a flexible, interconnected, and productive communication infrastructure. One of the most evident solutions for implementing such an infrastructure is the 5G platform. The basis for this statement is the 5G platform's support for three key technologies crucial for Industry 4.0: eMBB, mMTC, and NS. The eMBB technology is necessary to support seamless industrial virtual reality, the computational component of which is implemented in the cloud. The mMTC technology enables the energy-efficient connection of up to a million IIoT devices per square kilometre within the coverage area of a smart factory's active zone to the cloud. The NS technology allows organizing the communication space of the 5G ecosystem's base stations designed to ensure a defined level of quality of service for information interaction in the cyberspace of a smart factory. It is worth noting that the established level of the quality of service can influence the organization of the 5G ecosystem's communication resources in two scenarios: the scenario with Isolated Network Segments (INS scenario) and the scenario with Virtual Network Segments (VNS scenario).

Before formalizing the mentioned scenarios, let's define the types of requests characteristic of the described cyberspace of the smart factory. Considering the clustered structure of the 5G ecosystem of the smart factory, we will identify four permissible classes of requests for organizing the session of information interaction:

- eMBB and mMTC requests redirected to the target base station from outside (from other base stations in the 5G ecosystem structure): labelled as ee and em requests, respectively.

- eMBB and mMTC requests originating within the coverage of the target 5G base station (internal requests): labelled as ie and im requests, respectively.

Let's assume that any base station in the structure of the 5G ecosystem has $B > 1$ communication channels at its disposal. The set B consists of two subsets B_e, B_{em} , where the subset $B_e < B$ generalizes the volume of communication units intended to support only ee and ie requests, and the subset $B_{em} = B - B_e$ generalizes the volume of communication units intended to support all four types of requests (ee, em, ie, im requests). The INS scenario entails that no unit of communication resource can be transferred from one subset of the set B to another.

Each base station in the 5G ecosystem processes four Poissonian input request streams (corresponding to the number of distinctive types of input requests) arriving with intensities $\eta_{\{ee,em,ie,im\}}$, respectively. The channel resource utilization time for the characterized typed requests follows exponential distributions (with an average utilization time $1/\mu_e$ for two types of eMBB requests and an average utilization time $1/\mu_m$ for two types of mMTC requests). The exponential distribution lacks a memory effect. This particular circumstance allows us to ignore the categorization of input requests into internal and external when determining the performance indicators μ_e and μ_m .

Let's describe the procedure for accepting typed incoming requests by a base station in the 5G ecosystem, focusing on eMBB requests. If, at the moment of arrival of a ie request, there is at least one free unit of channel resources in the B_e subset, the ie request is accepted and occupies it. Otherwise, the incoming ie request is lost. Similarly, if, at the moment of arrival of a ee request, there is at least one free unit of channel resources in the B_e subset, the ee request is accepted and occupies it. Otherwise, if there is at least one free unit of channel resources in the B_{em} subset and the number of engaged units of channel resources in the B_{em} subset (due to accepted ee requests) is less than the threshold $T_{ee}, 1 \leq T_{ee} \leq B_{em}$, the incoming ee request is accepted. Otherwise, the incoming ee request is lost. It is worth noting that the average utilization time for the accepted ee request of a unit of channel resources from the B_{em} subset is characterized by the value $1/\mu_e$. Now let's focus on mMTC requests. If, at the moment of arrival of a im request, there is at least one free unit of channel resources in the B_{em} subset and the number of engaged units of channel resources in the B_{em} subset (due to accepted im requests) is less than the threshold $T_{im}, 1 \leq T_{im} \leq B_{em} - 1$, the incoming im request is accepted.

Otherwise, the incoming im request is lost. If, at the moment of arrival of a em request, there is at least one free unit of channel resources in the B_{em} subset, the em request is accepted and occupies it. Otherwise, the incoming em request is lost.

As a metric for evaluating the quality of service for $\{ee, em, ie, im\}$ requests, we will introduce the set of loss probabilities for incoming requests of the specified types: $\{Q_{ee}, Q_{em}, Q_{ie}, Q_{im}\}$, where indices ee and em characterize eMBB and mMTC requests redirected to the target base station from outside (from other base stations in the 5G ecosystem structure), respectively, and indices ie and im characterize eMBB and mMTC requests originating within the coverage of the target 5G base station (internal requests), respectively. The subsequent theoretical material is focused on the analytical formalization of these qualitative indicators for the target 5G ecosystem of the smart factory, organized according to the INS or VNS scenario.

2.2. Calculation method of quality of service metric for an instance of a smart factory 5G ecosystem operating within the INS scenario

The logic of processing incoming requests by the investigated system, described in Section 2.1, allows us to determine the probability of their loss through a similar metric recognized for an Erlang-type $M/M/B_e/0$ queuing system (Erlang B formula) with a load of $c_e = (\eta_{ie} + \eta_{ee})/\mu_e$. Generalizing the statement through the Erlang B formula [39] yields an equation

$$Q_{ie} = Er_B(c_e, B_e). \quad (1)$$

Taking into account that, under the conditions defined in Section 2.1, incoming ee requests may be accepted for service using communication resources indexed in the subset B_{em} , we cannot adequately describe the probability of Q_{ee} with expression (1). However, by employing expression (1), we can determine the intensity of the situation when incoming ee requests are accepted for service through the communication resources indexed in the subset B_{em} : $\hat{\eta}_{ee} = \eta_{ee} Q_{ie}$.

To formalize the quality indicators $\{Q_{ee}, Q_{em}, Q_{im}\}$, let's examine an Erlang-type $M/M/B_{em}/0$ queuing system with incoming requests of type $\{ee, em, im\}$ arriving at the 5G base station with intensities $\{\eta_{ee}, \eta_{em}, \eta_{im}\}$, respectively. The average service time for requests of these types differs. Accordingly, the state of the investigated queuing system at any given moment is characterized by a two-component vector $\vec{k} = (k_m, k_e)$, where the parameter k_m represents the total number of requests of types em and im accepted by the 5G base station, and the parameter k_e represents the number of requests of type ee accepted by the 5G base station.

The dynamics of the vector \vec{k} are determined by the state space E of the corresponding Markov chain:

$$E = \left\{ k : k_m = \overline{0, B_{em}}; k_e = \overline{0, T_{ee}}; k_m + k_e \leq B_{em} \right\}. \quad (2)$$

The rules of processing $\{ee, em, im\}$ requests described in Section 2.1 allow determining infinitesimal characteristics $\lambda(k, k')$ as elements of the Λ -matrix of the Markov chain for which $k, k' \in E$:

$$\lambda(k, k') = \begin{cases} \eta_m \forall k_m < T_{im}, k' = k + v_1, \\ \eta_{em} \forall k_m \geq T_{im}, k' = k + v_1, \\ \hat{\eta}_{ee} \forall k_e < T_{ee}, k' = k + v_2, \\ k_m \mu_m \forall k' = k - v_1, \\ k_e \mu_e \forall k' = k - v_2, \\ 0 \forall else, \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

where $\eta_m = \eta_{im} + \eta_{em}$, $v_1 = (1, 0)$, $v_2 = (0, 1)$.

The analytical form of the state space (2) and infinitesimal characteristics (3) allows for classifying the corresponding Markov chain as irreducible. Consequently, for the investigated Markov chain, there exists a stationary regime, which we will characterize with the stationary probability $q(k)$, $k \in E$. The analytical expressions we seek for calculating the quality characteristics $\{Q_{ee}, Q_{em}, Q_{im}\}$ will be expressed through the marginal distributions of the previously defined Markov chain. Let's further develop this thesis.

Based on the features defined in Section 2.1 of the INS scenario, we emphasize that losses of ee requests occur at the moment of arrival of a ee request:

- in the information environment of the 5G base station, T_{ee} requests of this type are already being serviced. The probability of this event is characterized by the value $\delta(k_e, T_{ee}) + (1 - \delta(k_e, T_{ee}))$, $k \in E$, where $\delta(n, m)$ is the Kronecker delta;
- in the information environment of the 5G base station, fewer than T_{ee} requests of this type are being serviced, but there are no available communication resource units in the base station. The probability of this event is characterized by the value $\delta(k_m + k_e, B_{em})$, $k \in E$.

In summary, we can express this as follows:

$$Q_{ee} = \sum_{k \in E} q(k) \left(\delta(k_e, T_{ee}) + (1 - \delta(k_e, T_{ee})) \delta(k_m + k_e, B_{em}) \right). \quad (4)$$

Similar reasoning allows us to express the remaining sought qualitative characteristics, namely:

$$Q_{im} = \sum_{k \in E} q(k) I(k_m \geq T_{im}), \quad (5)$$

$$Q_{em} = \sum_{k \in E} q(k) \delta(k_m + k_e, B_{em}), \quad (6)$$

where $I(e)$ is the indicator function of the event e .

To calculate the defined quality metric $\{Q_{ee}, Q_{im}, Q_{em}\}$ through expressions (4)-(6), we first need to find the probabilities $q(k)$ as a result of solving the corresponding system of equilibrium equations. For large values k , this operation is characterized by high computational complexity. Let's try to overcome this limitation.

Considering the structure of the vector \vec{k} , we classify the Markov chain with the state space (2) as two-dimensional. Arnold's theorem [17] allows us to conclude that in such a chain, inverse circulation between states of k , $k + v_1$, $k + v_2$ is realized (the condition of local balance is satisfied). Based on this fact, we can assert that there exists a multiplicative solution

$$q(n, l) \begin{cases} \frac{c_m^n \hat{c}_{ee}^l}{n! l!} q(0, 0) \forall 0 \leq n \leq T_{im}, 0 \leq l \leq \min(T_{ee}, B_{em} - n), \\ \left(\frac{c_m}{c_{ee}} \right)^{T_{im}} \frac{c_{em}^n \hat{c}_{ee}^l}{n! l!} p(0, 0) \forall T_{im} + 1 \leq n \leq B_{em}, 0 \leq l \leq \min(T_{ee}, B_{em} - 1), \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

for any path $(0, 0), (1, 0), \dots, (n, 0), (n, 1), \dots, (n, l)$ between states of $(0, 0), (n, l)$ in the INS scenario, where the probability $q(0, 0)$ is expressed with the normalization condition for $\sum_{k \in E} q(k) = 1$, $c_m = \eta_m / \mu_m$, $c_{em} = \eta_{em} / \mu_m$, $\hat{c}_{ee} = \hat{\eta}_{ee} / \mu_e$.

Taking into account (7), we obtain computationally efficient expressions for calculating the quality indicators (4)-(6):

$$Q_{ee} = \sum_{n=0}^{B_{em} - T_{ee}} q(n, T_{ee}) + \sum_{n=B_{em} - T_{ee} + 1}^{B_{em}} q(n, B_{em} - n), \quad (8)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
Q_{im} = & \mathbb{I}(T_{im} \leq B_{em} - T_{ee}) \sum_{n=T_{im}}^{B_{em}} \sum_{l=0}^{\min(T_{ee}, B_{em}-n)} q(n, l) + \\
& + \mathbb{I}(T_{im} > B_{em} - T_{ee}) \left(\sum_{n=B_{em}-T_{ee}}^{T_{im}-1} q(n, B_{em} - n) + \sum_{n=T_{im}}^{B_{em}} \sum_{l=0}^{B_{em}-n} q(n, l) \right), \tag{9}
\end{aligned}$$

$$Q_{em} = \sum_{n=B_{em}-T_{ee}}^{B_{em}} q(n, B_{em} - n). \tag{10}$$

2.3. Calculation method of quality of service metric for an instance of a smart factory 5G ecosystem operating within the VNS scenario

Unlike the INS scenario, the VNS scenario involves organizing the smart factory 5G ecosystem's communication resources in the form of virtual network segments. Let's define this "virtualization" in terms introduced in Section 2.1. Therefore, a specific feature of the VNS scenario will be that after the completion of a support session for an e request, a released channel resource unit belonging to subset B_e moves to a subset B_{em} if an incoming e request claims the resources of the latter. Simultaneously, a channel resource unit belonging to a subset B_{em} and used to support the session of a e request moves to subset B_e . In essence, the handling of $\{ee, em, ie, im\}$ requests inherits the description presented in Section 2.1 for the INS scenario.

The competitive nature of the VNS scenario manifests itself already in the stage of the analytical formalization of the quality indicator Q_{ie} , which can no longer be defined by the expression (1). While preserving the structure of the vector \vec{k} , we describe the state space E of the Markov chain, considering the specificity of the VNS scenario implementation, with the expression

$$E = \left\{ k : k_m = \overline{0, B_{em}}; k_e = \overline{0, B_e + T_{ee}}; k_m + k_e \leq B \right\}. \tag{11}$$

The rules for processing $\{ee, em, im\}$ requests in the form of infinitesimal characteristics $\lambda(k, k') \in \Lambda$ for the Markov chain with the state space (11) can be generalized with the expression

$$\lambda(k, k') = \begin{cases} \eta_m \forall k_m < T_{im}, k' = k + v_1, \\ \eta_{em} \forall k_m \geq T_{im}, k' = k + v_1, \\ \eta_e \forall k_e < B_e, k' = k + v_2, \\ \eta_{ee} \forall B_e \leq k_e < B_e + T_{ee}, k' = k + v_2, \\ k_m \mu_m \forall k' = k - v_1, \\ k_e \mu_e \forall k' = k - v_2, \\ 0 \forall \text{else}, \end{cases} \quad (12)$$

where $\eta_e = \eta_{ie} + \eta_{ee}$, $k, k' \in E$.

Let's repeat the logic of transformations that allowed us to formalize the expression (7) in the context of applying the VNS scenario to the smart factory 5G ecosystem. As a result, we analytically characterize the stationary distribution of state probabilities (11) for the Markov chain, elements of the Λ -matrix of which are described by the expression (12):

$\forall T_{im} \leq B_{em} - T_{ee}$:

$$q(n, l) = \begin{cases} \frac{c_m^n c_e^l}{n! l!} q(0, 0) \forall 0 \leq n \leq T_{im}, 0 \leq l \leq B_e, \\ \left(\frac{c_m}{c_{em}} \right)^{T_{im}} \frac{c_{em}^n c_e^l}{n! l!} q(0, 0) \forall T_{im} + 1 \leq n \leq B_{em}, 0 \leq l \leq B_e, \\ \left(\frac{c_e}{c_{ee}} \right)^{B_e} \frac{c_m^n c_{ee}^l}{n! l!} q(0, 0) \forall 0 \leq n \leq T_{im}, B_e + 1 \leq l \leq B_e + T_{ee}, \\ \left(\frac{c_m}{c_{em}} \right)^{T_{im}} \left(\frac{c_e}{c_{ee}} \right)^{B_e} \frac{c_{em}^n c_{ee}^l}{n! l!} q(0, 0) \\ \forall T_{im} + 1 \leq n \leq B_{em} - 1, B_e + 1 \leq l \leq \min(B_e + T_{ee}, B - n), \end{cases} \quad (13)$$

$\forall T_{im} > B_{em} - T_{ee}$:

$$q(n,l) = \begin{cases} \frac{c_m^n c_e^l}{n! l!} q(0,0) \forall 0 \leq n \leq T_{im}, 0 \leq l \leq B_e, \\ \left(\frac{c_m}{c_{em}}\right)^{T_{im}} \frac{c_{em}^n c_e^l}{n! l!} q(0,0) \forall T_{im} + 1 \leq n \leq B_{em}, 0 \leq l \leq B_e, \\ \left(\frac{c_e}{c_{ee}}\right)^{B_e} \frac{c_m^n c_{ee}^l}{n! l!} q(0,0) \\ \forall 0 \leq n \leq T_{im}, B_e + 1 \leq l \leq \min(B_e + T_{ee}, B - n), \\ \left(\frac{c_m}{c_{em}}\right)^{T_{im}} \left(\frac{c_e}{c_{ee}}\right)^{B_e} \frac{c_{em}^n c_{ee}^l}{n! l!} q(0,0) \\ \forall T_{im} + 1 \leq n \leq B_{em} - 1, B_e + 1 \leq l \leq B - n, \end{cases} \quad (14)$$

where the probability $q(0,0)$ is expressed with the normalization condition for $\sum_{k \in E} q(k) = 1$, $c_m = \eta_m / \mu_m$, $c_{ee} = \eta_{ee} / \mu_e$.

Quality indicators Q_{im} , Q_{ee} for the VNS scenario are determined analogously to what was described in Section 2.2 for the INS scenario: in the form of expressions (4), and (5), respectively. In turn, we formalize quality indicators 's' for the VNS scenario as

$$Q_{ie} = \sum_{k \in E} q(k) I(k_e \geq B_e), \quad (15)$$

$$Q_{em} = \sum_{k \in E} q(k) \left(\delta(k_m, B_{em}) + (1 - \delta(k_m, B_{em})) \delta(k_m + k_e, B_{em}) \right), \quad (16)$$

Based on expressions (13), and (14), we obtain computationally efficient dependencies for calculating the elements of the quality metric $\{Q_{ee}, Q_{em}, Q_{ie}, Q_{im}\}$, suitable for evaluating the situation when the smart factory 5G ecosystem operates within the VNS scenario:

$$Q_{ie} = \sum_{n=0}^{B_{em} - T_{ee}} \sum_{l=B_e}^{B_e + T_{ee}} q(n,l) + \sum_{n=B_{em} - T_{ee} + 1}^{B_{em}} \sum_{l=B_e}^{B-n} q(n,l), \quad (17)$$

$$Q_{ee} = \sum_{n=0}^{B_{em} - T_{ee}} q(n, B_e + T_{ee}) + \sum_{n=B_{em} - T_{ee} + 1}^{B_{em}} q(n, B - n), \quad (18)$$

$$Q_{im} = \sum_{n=T_{im}}^{B_{em}} \sum_{l=0}^{\min(B_e+T_{ee}, B-n)} q(n, l), \quad (19)$$

$$Q_{em} = \sum_{n=0}^{B_e-1} q(B_{em}, i) + \sum_{n=B_{em}-T_{ee}}^{B_{em}} q(n, B-n). \quad (20)$$

3 Results and Discussion

The generalized expressions (1), (8)-(10), or expressions (17)-(20) provide a conceptual framework for calculating the metric $\{Q_{ee}, Q_{em}, Q_{ie}, Q_{im}\}$ to assess the quality of request servicing in an instance of the smart factory 5G ecosystem operating under the rules defined by the INS or VNS scenarios, respectively. These scenarios generalize superpositions of parameter values that characterize the structure and load of the target 5G ecosystem. For the sake of simplifying simulation modelling, we will continue to use identical parameter values that characterize the load for both scenarios in the functioning of the investigated instance of the 5G ecosystem.

Let's consider that the number of communication units in subsets B_e , B_{em} is fixed, and the controlled parameters are the thresholds for T_{ee} , T_{im} . Therefore, increasing the value of each controlled parameter will positively impact the quality of servicing requests of the corresponding type, reducing the probability of servicing requests of other types (em , ie requests). Among the other parameters, the values of which will be common in the investigation of both INS and VNS scenarios, let's denote $B_{em} = 13$, $\eta_{ee} = 6$, $\eta_{em} = 3$, $\eta_{ie} = 10$, $\eta_{im} = 4$, $\mu_m = 2$. Separately, we will define two sets of parameters directly related to the processing of eMBB requests: $Set1 = \{B_e = 12, \mu_e = 1\}$, $Set2 = \{B_e = 3, \mu_e = 2\}$.

Let's set the value of the controlled parameter T_{ee} to the level of $T_{ee} = 2$. We will calculate dependencies for $Q_e = f(T_{im}, \{INS, VNS\}, \{e-req, i-req\})$, where $Q_e = Q_{ee} + Q_{ie}$; the composition $e-req$ generalizes the characteristics of all eMBB and mMTC requests (corresponding to ee and em requests, respectively) redirected to the target cluster of the investigated 5G ecosystem (hereinafter referred to as external requests); the composition $i-req$ generalizes the characteristics of all eMBB and mMTC requests (corresponding to ie and im requests, respectively) originating within the target 5G cluster (hereinafter referred to as internal requests). Fig. 1 visualizes graphs of the dependency of $Q_e = f(T_{im}, \{INS, VNS\}, \{e-req, i-req\})$ calculated for the set of $Set1$, and Fig. 2

visualizes graphs of the dependency of $Q_e = f(T_{im}, \{INS, VNS\}, \{e-req, i-req\})$ calculated for the set of *Set2*.

Fig. 1. Visualization of the dependency of $Q_e = f(T_{im}, \{INS, VNS\}, \{e-req, i-req\})$ calculated for the set of *Set1* at the level of $T_{ee} = 2$.

Fig. 2. Visualization of the dependency of $Q_e = f(T_{im}, \{INS, VNS\}, \{e-req, i-req\})$ calculated for the set of *Set2* at the level of $T_{ee} = 2$.

Let's analyze the results demonstrated in Fig. 1 and Fig. 2. Firstly, it is important to note that all the results presented in Section 3 do not claim universality but characterize only a specific instance of the 5G ecosystem. The parameters describing the structure and load of the latter are defined at the

beginning of Section 3. We made this clarification because, even from the graphs presented in Fig. 1 and Fig. 2, it is evident that the structure and load of the investigated 5G ecosystem have a significant impact on the calculated metrics for assessing the quality of service for eMBB and mMTC requests.

From the presented graphs in Fig. 1 and Fig. 2, a general trend is observed: in the long term, increasing the threshold value T_{im} does not lead to an increase in the probability of loss of eMBB requests in the investigated 5G ecosystem for both sets of controlled parameter values *Set1*, *Set2*. At the same time, it is worth noting that if access to the target 5G ecosystem is organized under the VNS scenario, then at small threshold values $1 \leq T_{im} \leq 3$, there is a noticeable increase in the probability of loss for both external and internal eMBB requests relative to the target 5G cluster. This trend is particularly evident for the set of *Set2* (Fig. 2). In the range of $T_{im} \in [1, 3]$ values, the metric Q_e increases with $\approx 25\%$ for both *i-req* (internal requests) and *e-req* (external requests). Overall, for both sets *Set1*, *Set2*, the VNS scenario for managing communication resources in the investigated 5G ecosystem is more productive in the eMBB-oriented metric Q_e (especially noticeable for external requests). Finally, comparing the graphs presented in Fig. 1 (*Set1*) with the graphs in Fig. 2 (*Set2*), it can be argued that the configurations encapsulated in the set *Set1* allow for a better quality of service for eMBB requests (the logic of forming the set of *Set1* tends to reduce the number of available channels for servicing eMBB requests while simultaneously increasing their speed characteristics).

Let's continue our investigation into the request servicing process in the 5G ecosystem using the metric Q_e . Now, the variable parameter is the threshold value T_{ee} within the range of $[1, 13]$ at a fixed threshold value of $T_{im} = 2$. The results of calculating the dependency $Q_e = f(T_{im}, \{INS, VNS\}, \{e-req, i-req\})$ are presented in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3. Visualization of the dependency

$$\lg Q_e = f(T_{ee}, \{INS, VNS\}, \{e\text{-req}, i\text{-req}\}) \text{ at a fixed threshold value of } T_{im} = 2.$$

During the calculation of the dependency $\lg Q_e = f(T_{ee}, \{INS, VNS\}, \{e\text{-req}, i\text{-req}\})$, it was found that the resulting graphs are entirely identical for both sets of *Set1*, *Set2*. Also, from Fig. 3, it is evident that the metric Q_e values, in the context of the quality of service for internal eMBB requests in the investigated 5G cluster, practically coincide with the entire range of argument values. Regarding the quality of service for external eMBB requests, it can be stated that the application of the INS scenario for organizing the information environment of the 5G ecosystem provides noticeably better results. This trend persists for the entire range of threshold T_{ee} values. Common to the description of the results presented in Fig. 1 and Fig. 2 is that active changes in the metric Q_e are observed in the same range of argument values: [1,3].

Generalizing the analysis of the results presented in Figs. 1-3, it can be noted that the tendencies in the dynamics of the metric Q_e values (characterizing the quality of service for eMBB requests in the investigated 5G ecosystem) caused by changes in the threshold values T_{im} are practically identical for the INS and VNS scenarios. However, their absolute values fall within different quantitative ranges. The demonstrated stabilization of the metric Q_e values with an increase in the argument values is achieved by the growing contribution of the Q_{ie} metric, calculated by expression (1) (for the INS scenario) and by expression (17) (for the VNS scenario), synchronously with the increase in argument values.

Let's now analyze the process of servicing mMTC requests in the investigated 5G ecosystem using the metric $Q_m = Q_{em} + Q_{im}$. The analysis will be conducted by

varying the threshold values T_{im} within the range of [1,13] at a fixed threshold value of $T_{ee} = 2$. The obtained dependency graphs $Q_m = f(T_{im}, \{INS, VNS\}, \{e-req, i-req\})$ calculated for the sets *Set1*, *Set2* are presented in Fig. 4 and Fig. 5, respectively.

Fig. 4. Visualization of the dependency of $\lg Q_m = f(T_{im}, \{INS, VNS\}, \{e-req, i-req\})$ calculated for the set of *Set1* at a fixed threshold value of $T_{ee} = 2$.

Fig. 5. Visualization of the dependency of $\lg Q_m = f(T_{im}, \{INS, VNS\}, \{e-req, i-req\})$ calculated for the set of *Set2* at a fixed threshold value of $T_{ee} = 2$.

From the graphs presented in Fig. 4 and Fig. 5, it is evident that the investigated 5G ecosystem (with settings both as *Set1* and *Set2*) better serves

internal mMTC requests as the T_{im} parameter increases. Importantly, this conclusion holds for both scenarios (INS, VNS) of organizing access to communication resources within the target 5G cluster. The fact that the probability of loss for external mMTC requests $\forall T_{im} \in [3,13]$ remains stable allows us to assert that the set of controlled parameters, on which experiments were conducted and the results of which are presented in Fig. 4 and Fig. 5, is optimally oriented towards servicing internal mMTC requests within the target 5G cluster. This optimization is achieved without any constraints on the quality of service for external mMTC, benefiting the entire investigated 5G ecosystem. If we pay attention to the nature of the $\lg Q_m = f(T_{im}, VNS, i - req, \{Set1, Set2\})$ graphs, it can be concluded that, while maintaining the trend of increasing the threshold value T_{im} beyond the upper limit of 13, the VNS scenario will become more promising than the INS scenario in the task of improving the quality of service for mMTC requests by the investigated 5G ecosystem.

Finally, let's conclude the cycle of experiments by investigating the process of managing the servicing of mMTC requests in the target cluster of the 5G ecosystem under varying threshold values T_{ee} within the range of $[1,13]$ at a fixed value of $T_{im} = 2$. The obtained graphs depicting the dependencies of $Q_m = f(T_{ee}, \{INS, VNS\}, \{e - req, i - req\})$, calculated for the sets of $Set1$, $Set2$, are presented in Fig. 6 and Fig. 7, respectively.

Fig. 6. Visualization of the dependency of $\lg Q_m = f(T_{ee}, \{INS, VNS\}, \{e - req, i - req\})$ calculated for the set of $Set1$ at a fixed value of $T_{im} = 2$.

Fig. 7. Visualization of the dependency of $\lg Q_m = f(T_{ee}, \{INS, VNS\}, \{e-req, i-req\})$ calculated for the set of *Set2* at a fixed value of $T_{im} = 2$.

Comparing the dependencies in Fig. 6 and Fig. 7, it can be observed that the similar-type graphs for Fig. 6 (*Set1*) and Fig. 7 (*Set2*) are virtually identical. Considering that the sets of parameters *Set1*, *Set2* characterize the dynamics of incoming eMBB requests, we can conclude that the communication resources in the target 5G cluster are sufficient for simultaneously servicing the defined streams of eMBB and mMTC requests. Additional confirmation of this conclusion is the practically static nature of the graphs presented in Fig. 6 and Fig. 7. The dynamics of the $\lg Q_m = f(T_{ee}, \{Set1, Set2\})$ dependencies are observed only at specific values of the T_{ee} parameter: $T_{ee} \in [1, 3]$. Additionally, it is noticeable ($\lg Q_m = f(T_{ee}, i-req)$ graphs) that varying the threshold value T_{ee} does not significantly affect the quality of the servicing process for internal mMTC requests in the target 5G cluster (for both INS and VNS scenarios). Meanwhile, the INS scenario allows for noticeably more effective servicing of external mMTC requests ($\lg Q_m = f(T_{ee}, e-req)$ graphs in Figs. 6, 7).

Summarizing, it can be noted that the values of the generalized metrics (1), (8)-(10), and (17)-(20) for evaluating the quality of servicing eMBB and mMTC requests in the clustered 5G ecosystem change very slowly relative to changes in the values of parameters generalized in the form of INS and VNS scenarios (except the $\lg Q_m = f(T_{im}, \{INS, VNS\}, i-req, \{Set1, Set2\})$ dependencies). This circumstance significantly simplifies the practical task of finding a configuration of characteristic parameter values for the 5G ecosystem capable of satisfying established constraints on the quality of servicing eMBB and mMTC requests in a

specific instance of such a system. For example, if the VNS request management scenario is implemented in the target 5G ecosystem, and compliance with the $Q_{ee} \leq 10^{-6}$ $Q_{ie} \leq 0.1$ requirements has to be guaranteed, it is sufficient for the conditions $T_{ee} \geq 3$, $T_{im} = 2$ to be satisfied (see Fig. 3). The flexibility formalized in Sections 2.2, 2.3 for INS and VNS scenarios, as well as the computational efficiency of expressions for calculating their respective metrics for evaluating the quality of servicing eMBB and mMTC requests in the clustered smart factory 5G ecosystem, provide practical value to the mathematical apparatus presented in the article.

4 Conclusions and Future Work

The paradigm of Industry 4.0 defines the future of industrial manufacturing through the tight integration of smart factories and the Industrial Internet of Things (IIoT). The informational component of this integration is expected to be based on a flexible, interconnected, and productive communication infrastructure. One of the most obvious solutions for implementing such infrastructure is the 5G platform. The basis for this assertion lies in the support provided by the 5G platform for three key technologies crucial to Industry 4.0: eMBB, mMTC, and NS.

NS technology allows the organization of the communication space within the 5G ecosystem's base stations, designed to ensure a defined level of quality of service for informational interaction in the cyberspace of a smart factory. It is considered that, to guarantee the established level of quality of service, the switching resources of the 5G ecosystem can be organized according to two scenarios: a scenario with Isolated Network Segments (INS) and a scenario with Virtual Network Segments (VNS). Considering the clustered structure of the 5G ecosystem in a smart factory, we examine four admissible classes of session setup requests: internal (within the target 5G cluster) and external (redirected to the target 5G cluster) eMBB requests, as well as internal and external mMTC requests. The article presents interpretations of metrics for assessing the quality of service for each of the identified request types, taking into account which of the two scenarios for processing eMBB and mMTC requests is implemented in the investigated 5G ecosystem. Analytical expressions for calculating quality indicators as part of the metrics are formalized based on the stationary probability distributions of states in corresponding two-dimensional Markov chains. Experiments were conducted to evaluate the quality of service for eMBB and mMTC requests in an instance of a clustered 5G ecosystem, considering the characteristics of its load. Empirical values of segmentation thresholds for communication resources of the target 5G cluster were obtained, oriented towards the efficient servicing of each of the mentioned request types.

Further research is planned to focus on detailing the two-dimensional Markov chains, whose stationary probability distributions form the basis for the analytical formalization of characteristics within the quality metric. In particular, there are plans to incorporate features such as instantaneous feedback and varying intensity of incoming flows of different types of requests.

Acknowledgement: This research is part of the project No. 2022/45/P/ST7/03450 co-funded by the National Science Centre and the European Union Framework Programme for Research and Innovation Horizon 2020 under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No. 945339. For the purpose of Open Access, the author has applied a CC-BY public copyright licence to any Author Accepted Manuscript (AAM) version arising from this submission.

Conflicts of Interest: The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Data Availability Statement: Most data are contained within the article. All the data are available on request.

References

- 1 Allioui H, Mourdi Y. Exploring the Full Potentials of IoT for Better Financial Growth and Stability: A Comprehensive Survey. *Sensors*. MDPI AG; 2023. p. 8015. doi:10.3390/s23198015
- 2 Ahmed SF, et al. Industrial Internet of Things enabled technologies, challenges, and future directions. *Computers and Electrical Engineering*. Elsevier BV; 2023. p. 108847. doi:10.1016/j.compeleceng.2023.108847
- 3 Trabelsi R, Fersi G, Jmaiel M. Access control in Internet of Things: A survey. *Computers & Security*. Elsevier BV; 2023. p. 103472. doi:10.1016/j.cose.2023.103472
- 4 Auzinger W, et al. A Continuous Model for States in CSMA/CA-Based Wireless Local Networks Derived from State Transition Diagrams. *Proceedings of International Conference on Data Science and Applications*. Springer Singapore; 2021. pp. 571–579. doi:10.1007/978-981-16-5348-3_45
- 5 Farooq MS, et al. A Survey on the Role of Industrial IoT in Manufacturing for Implementation of Smart Industry. *Sensors*. MDPI AG; 2023. p. 8958. doi:10.3390/s23218958
- 6 Wójcicki K, et al. Internet of Things in Industry: Research Profiling, Application, Challenges and Opportunities—A Review. *Energies*. MDPI AG; 2022. p. 1806. doi:10.3390/en15051806
- 7 Sufyan A, et al. From 5G to beyond 5G: A Comprehensive Survey of Wireless Network Evolution, Challenges, and Promising Technologies. *Electronics*. MDPI AG; 2023. p. 2200. doi:10.3390/electronics12102200

- 8 Kovtun V, Grochla K, Polys K. The concept of network resource control of a 5G cluster focused on the smart city's critical infrastructure needs. *Alexandria Engineering Journal*. Elsevier BV; 2024. pp. 248–256. doi:10.1016/j.aej.2024.03.038
- 9 Selmenska Z, et al. Investigation of Reading Convenience Factors Based on Graph Theory and Systems Analysis. *Lecture Notes in Networks and Systems*. Springer International Publishing; 2022. pp. 339–349. doi:10.1007/978-3-031-03877-8_30
- 10 Ogbodo EU, Abu-Mahfouz AM, Kurien AM. A Survey on 5G and LPWAN-IoT for Improved Smart Cities and Remote Area Applications: From the Aspect of Architecture and Security. *Sensors*. MDPI AG; 2022. p. 6313. doi:10.3390/s22166313
- 11 Kovtun V, Grochla K, Zaitseva E, Levashenko V. The concept of optimal planning of a linearly oriented segment of the 5G network. Balfaqih M, editor. *PLOS ONE*. Public Library of Science (PLoS); 2024. p. e0299000. doi:10.1371/journal.pone.0299000
- 12 Liu Y, Tian L, Li C, Wu Y. Analyzing the competitiveness and strategies of Chinese mobile network operators in the 5G era. *Telecommunications Policy*. Elsevier BV; 2023. p. 102652. doi:10.1016/j.telpol.2023.102652
- 13 Kim MS, Kim J, Kim S. Korea's leadership in 5G and beyond: Footprints and futures. *Telecommunications Policy*. Elsevier BV; 2023. p. 102613. doi:10.1016/j.telpol.2023.102613
- 14 Sargam S, Gupta R, Sharma R, Jain K. Adoption of 5G in developing economies: A supply side perspective from India. *Telematics and Informatics*. Elsevier BV; 2023. p. 102034. doi:10.1016/j.tele.2023.102034
- 15 Alhloul A, Kiss E. Industry 4.0 as a Challenge for the Skills and Competencies of the Labor Force: A Bibliometric Review and a Survey. *Sci*. MDPI AG; 2022. p. 34. doi:10.3390/sci4030034
- 16 Khourshed NF, Elbarky SS, Elgamal S. Investigating the Readiness Factors for Industry 4.0 Implementation for Manufacturing Industry in Egypt. *Sustainability*. MDPI AG; 2023. p. 9641. doi:10.3390/su15129641
- 17 Tubis AA, Grzybowska K. In Search of Industry 4.0 and Logistics 4.0 in Small-Medium Enterprises—A State of the Art Review. *Energies*. MDPI AG; 2022. p. 8595. doi:10.3390/en15228595
- 18 Huang J, et al. Opportunistic capacity based resource allocation for 6G wireless systems with network slicing. *Future Generation Computer Systems*. Elsevier BV; 2023. pp. 390–401. doi:10.1016/j.future.2022.10.032
- 19 S. S, Mishra S, Hota C. Joint QoS and energy-efficient resource allocation and scheduling in 5G Network Slicing. *Computer Communications*. Elsevier BV; 2023. pp. 110–123. doi:10.1016/j.comcom.2023.02.009

- 20 Shkarupylo VV, et al. On Applicability of Model Checking Technique in Power Systems and Electric Power Industry. *Systems, Decision and Control in Energy III*. Springer International Publishing; 2021. pp. 3–21. doi:10.1007/978-3-030-87675-3_1
- 21 Kumar R, Sinwar D, Singh V. QoS aware resource allocation for coexistence mechanisms between eMBB and URLLC: Issues, challenges, and future directions in 5G. *Computer Communications*. Elsevier BV; 2024. pp. 208–235. doi:10.1016/j.comcom.2023.10.024
- 22 Binti Abdul Rahim NF, et al. Channel Congestion Control in VANET for Safety and Non-Safety Communication: A Review. 2021 6th IEEE International Conference on Recent Advances and Innovations in Engineering (ICRAIE). IEEE; 2021. doi:10.1109/icraie52900.2021.9704017
- 23 Fedorchenko I, et al. Modified genetic algorithm to determine the location of the distribution power supply networks in the city. Zenodo. 2020. doi:10.5281/ZENODO.5163692
- 24 Ma Z, Li B, Yan Z, Yang M. QoS-Oriented joint optimization of resource allocation and concurrent scheduling in 5G millimeter-wave network. *Computer Networks*. Elsevier BV; 2020. p. 106979. doi:10.1016/j.comnet.2019.106979
- 25 Rehman AU, et al. Enhancement in Quality-of-Services using 5G cellular network using resource reservation protocol. *Physical Communication*. Elsevier BV; 2022. p. 101907. doi:10.1016/j.phycom.2022.101907
- 26 Zhang J, et al. Routing and scheduling co-design for holistic software-defined deterministic network. *Fundamental Research*. Elsevier BV; 2023. doi:10.1016/j.fmre.2023.11.007
- 27 Park K, Sung S, Kim H, Jung J. Technology trends and challenges in SDN and service assurance for end-to-end network slicing. *Computer Networks*. Elsevier BV; 2023. p. 109908. doi:10.1016/j.comnet.2023.109908
- 28 Dogani J, Namvar R, Khunjush F. Auto-scaling techniques in container-based cloud and edge/fog computing: Taxonomy and survey. *Computer Communications*. Elsevier BV; 2023. pp. 120–150. doi:10.1016/j.comcom.2023.06.010
- 29 Zhu Z, Li X, Chu Z. Three major operating scenarios of 5G: eMBB, mMTC, URLLC. *Intelligent Sensing and Communications for Internet of Everything*. Elsevier; 2022. pp. 15–76. doi:10.1016/b978-0-32-385655-3.00006-0
- 30 Chilwan A, Jiang Y. Modeling and Delay Analysis for SDN-based 5G Edge Clouds. 2020 IEEE Wireless Communications and Networking Conference (WCNC). IEEE; 2020. doi:10.1109/wcnc45663.2020.9120849

- 31 Silva GMF, Abrão T. Throughput and latency in the distributed Q-learning random access mMTC networks. *Computer Networks*. Elsevier BV; 2022. p. 108787. doi:10.1016/j.comnet.2022.108787
- 32 Kharchenko V, et al. AI Cybersecurity Assurance for Autonomous Transport Systems: Scenario, Model, and IMECA-Based Analysis. *Communications in Computer and Information Science*. Springer International Publishing; 2022. pp. 66–79. doi:10.1007/978-3-031-20215-5_6
- 33 Althumali H, et al. Priority-based load-adaptive preamble separation random access for QoS-differentiated services in 5G networks. *Journal of Network and Computer Applications*. Elsevier BV; 2022. p. 103396. doi:10.1016/j.jnca.2022.103396
- 34 Traboulsi S. Overview of 5G-oriented Positioning Technology in Smart Cities. *Procedia Computer Science*. Elsevier BV; 2022. pp. 368–374. doi:10.1016/j.procs.2022.03.049
- 35 Kovtun V, Grochla K, Altameem T, Al-Maitah M. Evaluation of the QoS policy model of an ordinary 5G smart city cluster with predominant URLLC and eMBB traffic. Nyangaresi VO, editor. *PLOS ONE*. Public Library of Science (PLoS); 2023. p. e0295252. doi:10.1371/journal.pone.0295252
- 36 Moges TH, Lakew DS, Nguyen NP, Dao N-N, Cho S. Cellular Internet of Things: Use cases, technologies, and future work. *Internet of Things*. Elsevier BV; 2023. p. 100910. doi:10.1016/j.iot.2023.100910
- 37 Wang B, Zheng P, Yin Y, Shih A, Wang L. Toward human-centric smart manufacturing: A human-cyber-physical systems (HCPS) perspective. *Journal of Manufacturing Systems*. Elsevier BV; 2022. pp. 471–490. doi:10.1016/j.jmsy.2022.05.005
- 38 Kovtun V, Grochla K. Investigation of the competitive nature of eMBB and mMTC 5G services in conditions of limited communication resource. *Scientific Reports*. Springer Science and Business Media LLC; 2022. doi:10.1038/s41598-022-20135-5
- 39 Wang J, et al. Erlang planning network: An iterative model-based reinforcement learning with multi-perspective. *Pattern Recognition*. Elsevier BV; 2022. p. 108668. doi:10.1016/j.patcog.2022.108668